

Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system

Standardisation of pan-Antarctic mooring and profiles

Deliverable D1.1

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Cover sheet: Credits to Shenjie Zhou (UKRI-BAS). Left: Total number of profiles contained within 50km×50km grid box over the Southern Ocean. Right: Position of moored time series south of 60°S in the compilation.

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1. Publishable summary

We gathered over 600,000 temperature/salinity profiles and time series observations of essential ocean variables (here ocean temperature, salinity, pressure and currents) that are repositied in various data centres and in various formats across the world. This heterogeneity creates a significant barrier for researchers trying to obtain a circumpolar view of ocean processes. Here, we provide version 1 of two compilation datasets merging observations from an extensive set of sources, and attempting to be as complete as possible. This open dataset will provide the observational backbone for OCEAN:ICE analysis and hopefully many other projects around the world. We are looking for continuing expanding both the profile compilations with the addition of early temperature measurement collected using eXpendable BathyThermograph (XBT), Mechanical Bathythermograph (MBT), early salinity measurement from bottle measurements, remaining mooring time series that is under embargo or under-processing with our contributor as listed above.

2. Work performed and main achievements

2.1 Description of the work performed

2.1.1 Profiles compilation

We gathered over 600,000 temperature and salinity profiles south of 45°S collected with ship-based CTD casts, Argo floats and Seal-borne profilers. The CTD casts are aggregated from several major data centres, including World Ocean Database (WOD), British Oceanographic Data Centre (BODC), Southern Ocean Data Base (SODB), CLIVAR and Carbon Hydrographic Data Office (CCHDO), Korean Polar Data Center (KPDC) and Pangaea Database. We obtained Argo floats data from https://nrlgodae1.nrlmry.navy.mil/cgi-bin/argo_select.pl, and Seal-borne profilers data from <https://meop.net/database/meop-databases/meop-ctd-database.html>.

2.1.1.a Data curation

We performed a duplication check on each profile by the recorded casting time and location. We used WOD data as the baseline and compared each WOD profiles with the data feeding in from other data centres. Taking SODB for example, the comparison starts by looping through all the WOD profiles and for each WOD profile we search through the SODB database for any profile within a certain spatial distance and temporal window. If such a profile is found in SODB, we flagged the profile(s) as duplication and removed it from SODB. At the end, we then append the remaining profiles, if there is any, to the original WOD dataset. The updated dataset (i.e., WOD+remaining SODB) is then treated as the new baseline for comparison with the dataset we obtained from the next data centres. The order of comparison is made on WOD against dataset from SODB, KPDC, CCHDO, BODC and Pangaea. The temporal window is set for 1 day (i.e., 12 hours before and after the particular cast that is being checked on) and the spatial distance threshold is set to be 1 km in the open ocean (water depth deeper than 1000 m) and 200 m in the shelf regions (water depth shallower than 1000 m). In cases where 2 or more CTD casts were identified within these temporal and spatial scales, we treat them as duplicates and only use one cast – the one with better/best vertical resolution. If duplicated casts are identical, we retain the one from the WOD database.

Only profiles flagged good in position and time are used for this compilation. Within each profile, only flagged good temperature and salinity measurements were retained. A linear interpolation is then applied to all profiles (after the flagged bad values were removed from each profile) with a 10 dbar interval to standardise the profile dimension for easier assembling into NetCDF format.

2.1.1.b NetCDF file content information

The profiles compilation consists of two NetCDF files, one for conservative temperature (CT) profile records and the other one for the absolute salinity (SA) profile records. Each NetCDF file contains the same variables except for the hydrographic variables. See below Table 1 for an overview of the NetCDF files content for temperature compilation.

Table 1. Overview of the profile compilation file content

Variables	Description
lon	Longitude (Degree East)
lat	Latitude (Degree North)
dyr	Date of profile collection in days since 1950-01-01 00:00:00)
source_flag	Data source flag; 1 = WOD; 2 = SODB; 3 = KPDC; 4 = CCHDO; 5 = BODC; 6 = Pangaea; 7 = Argo; 8 = MEOP

instrument_type_flag	Instrument type flag; 1 = CTD; 2 = OSD; 3 = XBT; 4 = MBT; 5 = Argo profiler; 6 = seal-borne profiler;
pres	Standard water pressure for all profiles from 5 to 6005 dbar at an interval of 10 dbar.
ct/sa	Conservative temperature or Absolute Salinity computed using GSW toolbox from in-situ temperature and practical salinity
bathy	Local water depth for each profile
doi	External source links for each profile, for WOD CTD profiles, the unique cast ID is provided, and for KPDC dataset, the PI name and cruise code is provided
access_date	The date of access to the data centres in days since 1950-01-01 00:00:00

2.1.2 Timeseries compilation

We gathered all the publicly available moored time series of temperature, salinity, current velocity (meridional and zonal components) and pressure (if recorded) around Antarctica, with a focus on the continental shelf region (including borehole measurements and shelf moorings). The northern limit is set to be 60°S, meaning some open ocean moored time series are also included. Moored time series recovered from each mooring instruments are grouped into one NetCDF file. For the first version of moored time series collection, we collected 345 time series, these include instances where one mooring site has had multiple revisits.

Further expansion of this mooring collection is underway, and we are looking into incorporating moorings near the West Antarctic Peninsula, western Amundsen Sea to have a most complete moored time series coverage. A map of version 1 mooring records location is provided in the cover sheet above. See Table 2 below an overview of the mooring file content.

Table 2. Overview of the moored time series file content

Variables	Description
lon	Longitude (Degree East)
lat	Latitude (Degree North)
bottom_depth	bottom depth of the mooring location
doi	doi links or downloadable links to the original dataset, or the name of point of contact for accessing the dataset.
Instrument_id_var	instrument is labelled with numeric index (e.g., 01, 02, 03 etc.) followed by archived variables (e.g., u, v, w, temp, salin, depth, press, date, etc.) NetCDF attribution information provides with further information of the instrument type and details of the instrument manufacturer (if applicable)

2.2 Open Science

This data products are directly available through SEANOE. The profiles compilation can be accessed via <https://doi.org/10.17882/99787>. The moored time series collection can be accessed via <https://doi.org/10.17882/99922>.

3. Results

3.1 Achieved results

Our results are two new compilations described above and in the following section. They will both contribute to OCEAN:ICE research and research from the wider, global community.

3.2 Datasets

PID (type of persistent identifier)	Type of PID	Brief description of the dataset	URL to repository
10.17882/99787	DOI	Southern Ocean (90°S-45°S) conservative temperature and absolute salinity profiles compilation	https://doi.org/10.17882/99787
10.17882/99922	DOI	Southern Ocean moored time series (south of 60°S) version 1 (OCEAN:ICE D1.1)	https://doi.org/10.17882/99922

4. Impact

4.1 Contribution to the project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the following objectives indicated in the Description of the Action.

O1: Reduce the spatial and knowledge gaps in ocean observations around Antarctica.

Given to Antarctic's remoteness and position within a variety of oceanic regimes with an open Southern Ocean in the North, marginal ice zones further South and the crucial role played by Antarctic shelf seas, the techniques used to measure ocean temperature, salinity, pressure and currents is more variable than in open oceans, and observations tend to be scattered in various national data centres, personal researcher repositories, and in various format. As such, one critical gap limiting circum-Antarctic analyses is the lack of circum-Antarctic compilations. As far as we are aware, our compilation is the most complete to date, and provides the critical first step allowing researchers within OCEAN:ICE and the wider community to understand both regional and circum-Antarctic variability of ocean properties, their drivers, and their impacts.

O2: Improve critical ice sheet-ocean processes in numerical models.

This dataset will be crucially used to constrain models, which are key tools to improve our understanding of ice/ocean interactions, yet remain poorly constrained to date.

O3: Improve representation of AIS dynamics and integrate this knowledge into ice sheet-climate models.

Similarly, this dataset can be used to provide oceanic boundary conditions (and their variability) for ice sheet models.

O4: Quantify AIS melt sensitivity to climate forcing and reduce the ‘deep uncertainty’ in freshwater flux and SLR projections to 2300.

Whilst not directly answering the deep uncertainty question on freshwater fluxes, this compilation will be used to measure the integral of the fluxes (heat and salt content) in the ocean, whilst the variability of that integral does constrain fluxes, indirectly.

O5: Assess how global ocean circulation is impacted by freshwater discharge from the northern and southern ice sheets.

This objective is beyond the scope of this data delivery. However, the models and data analysis used to answer this objective will make use of this dataset.

O7: Deliver free and open data access and contribute to international assessments, climate model development, observing initiatives and policymakers.

This data release is free and open, so will clearly contribute to further our understanding of the Southern Ocean/Antarctic shelf seas system, their interactions with the Antarctic ice sheet, and thereby contribute to international assessments, direct future observing initiatives, and policy response to improved understanding of global sea level rise uncertainties and the associated impact for coastal protections.